

Cation Exchange Studies of Eleven Ions in DMSO-HCl, DMSO-HNO₃, Acetone-HCl and Acetone-HNO₃ Systems : A Selective Separation of Bismuth from Numerous Metal Ions

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The sorption of Mg²⁺, Ca²⁺, Sr²⁺, Ba²⁺, Mn²⁺, Co²⁺, Ni²⁺, Cu²⁺, Zn²⁺, Cd²⁺ and Bi³⁺ has been studied in DMSO-HCl, DMSO-HNO₃, acetone-HCl and acetone-HNO₃ systems. The organic component-1M acid ratio is 1 : 9, 2 : 8, 3 : 7, 4 : 6, 5 : 5, 6 : 4, 7 : 3, 8 : 2 and 9 : 1 (v/v). The sorption of these ions has also been studied in pure solvents and 1M acid media. As a result of this study the following separations have been achieved : Cu-Ni, Cd-Zn, Ni-Co, Zn-Cu-Mn, Zn-Cu-Co and Bi from numerous metal ions.

DMSO is a useful solvent for ion exchange studies. It has a high dielectric constant and is miscible in water¹. It has two coordinating centres, a hard oxygen atom and a soft sulfur atom. It acts as a very strong ligand for many cations^{2,3}. Due to its strong coordinating power for cations and its weak interaction with anions⁴ there are numerous cation separation possibilities by ion exchange in this solvent.

DMSO has a specific interaction for H⁺ ions and it solvates strongly most metal ions removing the water molecules from the coordinating spheres of the aquo ions. Cl⁻ becomes a stronger nucleophile⁵ in DMSO-HCl systems and the formation of chlorocomplexes is favoured. The lower dielectric constant of DMSO (46.6) as compared to that of water (81.7) favours the formation of non-dissociated chlorocomplexes⁶. It exhibits a specific interaction for Ag⁺ ions and for some other metal ions which have not yet been fully explained. This solvent, therefore, offers attractive possibilities for ion exchange studies which may lead to interesting separations depending upon the strength and the nature of the chlorocomplexes formed.

Bi is an important element and its separation from Cu, Co, Ni, Mn, Zn, Cd and alkaline earths is useful. Some methods are available for the separation of Bi(III) from Zn, Cd⁷, Cu(II)⁸, Fe(III) and Pb(II)^{9,10}. Bi(III) has also been separated from Cd, Co, Ni, Cu(II), Ca, Mg and Zn using a KU-2 cation exchange resin¹¹. The column was eluted with 0.1M (CH₂)₆N₄ which converts Bi(III) into the hydroxylated form. The quantitative aspects of this separation were not studied and it appears that there should be considerable tailing.

Keeping in mind the above, we tried to study under similar conditions the separation possibilities

of DMSO-HCl, DMSO-HNO₃, acetone-HCl and acetone-HNO₃ systems. As a result we have been able to pin point the role of DMSO and HCl in the ion exchange of metal ions. At the same time some useful separations e.g., (i) Cd from Zn and (ii) Bi from numerous metal ions have also been achieved.

Experimental

Reagents : Resins, Dowex 50W-X8, 20-50 mesh, H⁺ form resin was used throughout the study. The resin was allowed to swell before use. It was purified, washed, air dried and stored in a plastic air-tight bottle.

The DMSO was Lab. Chem. grade (Cambrian Chemicals Co., Crydon). Acetone, the chlorides of Mg, Cu, Sr, Ba, Zn, Cd and Cu, the nitrates of Mn and Bi and the sulphates of Ni and Co were AnalaR grade (B.D.H.).

Procedure : The solvent systems used in this study were prepared as follows : DMSO and aqueous 1M HCl were mixed in volume by volume ratios of 1 : 9, 2 : 8, 3 : 7, 4 : 6, 5 : 5, 6 : 4, 7 : 3, 8 : 2, 9 : 1 to give solvent systems S₁-S₉ respectively. HCl was replaced by aqueous HNO₃ of the same molarity and mixed in the above ratios to give solvent system S₁₀-S₁₈. In systems S₁-S₉ and S₁₀ to S₁₈ the DMSO was replaced by acetone to give solvent systems S₁₉-S₂₇ and S₂₈-S₃₆ respectively. The solvents DMSO, acetone, 1M HNO₃, and 1M HCl have been called S₃₇, S₃₈, S₃₉ and S₄₀ systems respectively.

The sorption by the resin is expressed as a mass distribution coefficient, K_d defined by equation (1)

$$K_d = \frac{V_1 - V_2}{V_2} \times 50 \quad \dots (1)$$

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where V_1 and V_2 are the volumes in ml of $10^{-3}M$ EDTA used for 0.5 ml metal ion solution before and after sorption respectively on 0.5 g of resin in 25 ml of the solvent systems.

The K_d values were determined by the batch process. In this process, exactly weighed 0.5 g samples of dry resin were equilibrated with 0.5 ml of the metal stock solution (containing 0.3 m mole of the metal ion except Bi which was only 0.2 m mole) and with 25 ml of the solvent mixture in 100 ml erlenmeyer flasks. The contents were allowed to stand for 24 hrs at room temperature. They were shaken intermittently during this period.

The resin was separated from the solution. The solution was then evaporated to dryness, dissolved in water and titrated. The results have been summarized in Tables 1-4.

The separations were achieved by the column process. In this process 10-12 cm long columns with an inner diameter of 0.8 cm were packed with the resin. After conditioning, the column was eluted with 5 ml fractions of the eluant at a flow rate of 0.5-0.7 ml/min. The collected fractions were then titrated. The results have been summarized in Tables 5-6.

TABLE 1— K_d * VALUES FOR 11 METAL IONS IN DMSO-1M HCl SYSTEMS

Ey means 10^y

Metal Ions	DMSO, (%v/v)		30	40	50	60	70	80	90	100
	10	20								
Mg ⁺⁺	1.8 E1	2.2 E1	2.8 E1	4.0 E1	5.6 E1	6.4 E1	1.0 E1	1.4 E2	1.1 E2	5.6 E1
Ca ⁺⁺	3.2 E1	4.0 E1	7.1 E1	1.4 E2	3.2 E2	6.8 E2	1.2 E3	1.8 E3	1.5 E3	3.2 E2
Sr ⁺⁺	5.6 E1	8.0 E1	1.3 E2	2.0 E2	3.5 E2	6.9 E2	1.1 E3	1.8 E3	6.3 E2	4.1 E2
Ba ⁺⁺	1.2 E2	2.8 E2	5.8 E2	1.0 E3	1.8 E3	3.7 E3	3.7 E3	7.4 E3	C.A.	C.A.
Mn ⁺⁺	7.0 E0	1.0 E1	1.8 E1	2.5 E1	5.6 E1	7.1 E1	9.0 E1	1.3 E2	1.7 E2	1.2 E3
Co ⁺⁺	2.5 E1	3.6 E1	4.5 E1	5.7 E1	7.1 E1	9.0 E1	1.2 E2	1.6 E2	1.5 E2	5.0 E1
Ni ⁺⁺	4.0 E1	1.1 E2	1.4 E2	2.1 E2	2.8 E2	3.7 E2	4.0 E2	6.4 E2	6.4 E2	1.2 E2
Cu ⁺⁺	1.2 E1	2.3 E1	3.1 E1	4.5 E1	4.7 E1	3.2 E1	2.3 E1	2.0 E1	1.8 E1	8.6 E1
Zn ⁺⁺	1.5 E1	2.5 E1	1.3 E1	1.5 E1	4.8 E0	5.8 E0	8.0 E0	1.0 E1	2.5 E1	1.2 E2
Cd ⁺⁺	1.0 E1	1.1 E1	1.4 E1	1.5 E1	1.6 E1	2.1 E1	2.2 E1	1.4 E1	1.1 E1	1.4 E2
Bi ⁺⁺	7.0 E0	1.1 E1	1.8 E1	2.5 E1	3.2 E1	3.6 E1	4.0 E1	1.2 E1	6.6 E0	1.0 E2

* Average of atleast two replicates.

TABLE 2— K_d * VALUES FOR 11 METAL IONS IN DMSO-1M HNO₃ SYSTEMS

Ey means 10^y

Metal Ions	DMSO, (%v/v)		30	40	50	60	70	80	90	100
	10	20								
Mg ⁺⁺	1.8 E1	2.2 E1	2.5 E1	3.2 E1	4.5 E1	5.0 E1	6.5 E1	7.2 E1	6.2 E1	7.0 E0
Ca ⁺⁺	2.2 E1	3.2 E1	5.6 E1	1.2 E2	2.5 E2	5.0 E2	6.8 E2	5.8 E2	4.5 E2	1.3 E1
Sr ⁺⁺	5.6 E1	8.0 E1	1.3 E2	2.0 E2	2.5 E2	3.1 E2	4.0 E2	4.5 E2	4.2 E2	3.5 E1
Ba ⁺⁺	1.3 E2	2.0 E2	3.1 E2	4.0 E2	6.8 E2	8.9 E2	1.4 E3	3.7 E3	C.A.	1.1 E2
Mn ⁺⁺	1.6 E1	2.0 E1	3.5 E1	4.0 E1	7.1 E1	1.1 E2	1.8 E2	2.5 E2	2.6 E2	1.4 E1
Co ⁺⁺	8.0 E1	8.9 E1	1.0 E2	1.1 E2	1.3 E2	1.4 E2	1.8 E2	1.9 E2	2.0 E2	3.2 E1
Ni ⁺⁺	7.0 E1	7.1 E1	7.2 E1	1.0 E2	1.1 E2	1.8 E2	2.8 E2	3.6 E2	4.0 E2	1.9 E1
Cu ⁺⁺	2.8 E1	3.5 E1	4.0 E1	5.6 E1	6.4 E1	7.1 E1	8.0 E1	1.0 E2	1.3 E2	1.6 E1
Zn ⁺⁺	3.1 E1	3.2 E1	3.2 E1	4.8 E1	7.9 E1	1.6 E2	1.0 E2	6.4 E1	4.0 E1	1.6 E1
Cd ⁺⁺	3.1 E1	2.8 E1	3.5 E1	5.0 E1	7.9 E1	4.6 E1	5.1 E1	5.6 E1	7.0 E1	1.4 E1
Bi ⁺⁺	7.4 E2	1.2 E3	1.4 E3	1.7 E2	1.8 E2	2.0 E2	2.2 E2	2.8 E2	5.1 E2	4.7 E2

* Average of atleast two replicates.

TABLE 3— K_d * VALUES FOR 11 METAL IONS IN ACETONE-1M HCl SYSTEMS

Ey means 10^y

Metal Ions	Acetone, (%v/v)		30	40	50	60	70	80	90	1M HCl
	10	20								
Mg ⁺⁺	1.1 E1	1.3 E1	2.0 E1	4.0 E1	5.6 E1	7.9 E1	1.4 E2	3.5 E2	5.3 E2	1.6 E1
Ca ⁺⁺	1.3 E1	1.6 E1	1.8 E1	5.6 E1	7.9 E1	1.3 E2	1.8 E2	3.7 E2	4.2 E2	2.5 E1
Sr ⁺⁺	5.6 E1	6.4 E1	1.0 E2	1.4 E2	2.5 E2	3.6 E2	5.8 E2	8.9 E2	1.0 E3	4.6 E1
Ba ⁺⁺	1.2 E2	1.6 E2	2.0 E2	3.8 E2	5.8 E2	7.8 E2	1.0 E3	1.2 E3	1.2 E3	1.2 E2
Mn ⁺⁺	5.4 E0	1.4 E1	2.2 E1	4.0 E1	7.9 E1	1.0 E2	1.2 E2	2.0 E2	3.2 E2	5.6 E0
Co ⁺⁺	6.4 E0	1.1 E1	1.8 E1	3.2 E1	6.4 E1	1.0 E2	1.6 E2	3.2 E2	5.0 E2	2.3 E1
Ni ⁺⁺	1.0 E1	1.8 E1	2.5 E1	5.0 E1	8.9 E1	1.3 E2	2.0 E2	3.2 E2	3.6 E2	3.2 E1
Cu ⁺⁺	1.4 E0	6.2 E0	1.6 E1	2.8 E1	3.5 E1	1.2 E2	1.0 E2	7.3 E1	4.0 E2	1.6 E1
Zn ⁺⁺	1.0 E1	8.8 E0	8.4 E0	8.4 E0	8.0 E0	6.2 E0	5.0 E0	4.0 E0	2.5 E0	2.0 E1
Cd ⁺⁺	1.3 E1	8.8 E0	9.8 E0	1.1 E1	8.4 E0	8.8 E0	9.1 E0	7.6 E0	5.0 E0	1.0 E1
Bi ⁺⁺	1.4 E1	1.6 E1	1.8 E1	3.1 E1	2.5 E1	1.4 E1	1.1 E1	8.0 E0	6.2 E0	4.2 E0

* Average of atleast two replicates.

TABLE 4— K_d^* VALUES FOR 11 METAL IONS IN ACETONE-1M HNO_3 SYSTEMS

Ey means 10^y

Metal Ions	Acetone, (%v/v)		30	40	50	60	70	80	90	100
	10	20								
Mg ²⁺	2.0 E1	2.5 E1	4.0 E1	6.5 E1	1.3 E2	3.2 E2	5.8 E2	1.2 E3	1.9 E3	1.4 E2
Ca ²⁺	2.5 E1	4.5 E1	9.0 E1	2.0 E2	2.5 E2	3.2 E2	4.1 E2	1.1 E3	1.2 E2	3.8 E3
Sr ²⁺	5.6 E1	1.1 E2	1.8 E2	6.3 E2	1.4 E3	2.4 E3	2.4 E3	3.7 E3	G.A.	C.A.
Ba ²⁺	1.2 E2	2.0 E2	3.6 E2	7.8 E2	1.4 E3	2.4 E3	3.7 E3	7.4 E3	G.A.	ppt.
Mn ²⁺	1.7 E1	2.2 E1	5.1 E1	1.1 E2	1.6 E2	2.1 E2	6.5 E2	1.2 E3	1.8 E3	3.7 E3
Co ²⁺	1.1 E2	1.6 E2	2.0 E2	4.1 E2	7.1 E2	1.0 E3	1.0 E3	1.4 E3	1.8 E3	3.7 E3
Ni ²⁺	8.0 E1	1.0 E2	1.3 E2	1.8 E2	3.6 E2	5.3 E2	1.8 E3	1.8 E3	1.8 E3	7.2 E2
Cu ²⁺	1.5 E1	4.6 E1	8.0 E1	1.4 E2	3.2 E2	1.0 E3	1.2 E3	2.0 E3	3.7 E3	3.2 E2
Zn ²⁺	2.0 E1	3.2 E1	7.1 E1	1.0 E2	2.5 E2	5.3 E2	6.5 E2	4.0 E2	8.0 E1	5.0 E1
Cd ²⁺	2.0 E1	3.2 E1	5.0 E1	7.1 E1	1.8 E2	3.2 E2	3.7 E2	5.0 E2	6.3 E2	1.0 E2
Bi ³⁺	3.7 E3	3.7 E3	7.4 E3	2.4 E3	1.8 E3	1.2 E3	8.9 E2	8.9 E2	8.0 E2	1.0 E3

* Average of atleast two replicates.

TABLE 5—QUANTITATIVE SEPARATIONS OF SYNTHETIC MIXTURE OF METAL IONS ON COLUMNS (0.8 × 10 cm) PACKED WITH DOWEX 50WX8 RESIN

Metal ions	Eluent, Vol. ml	Taken m mole	Found* m mole
Cu ^a	35	0.120	0.120 ± .002
Ni ^b	60	0.143	0.144 ± .001
Cd ^d	40	0.128	0.126 ± .003
Zn ^a	60	0.143	0.143 ± .001
Co ^a	45	0.150	0.148 ± .002
Ni ^a	60	0.143	0.142 ± .002
Zn ^c	60	0.143	0.141 ± .001
Cu ^a	40	0.120	0.120 ± .001
Mn ^b	80	0.133	0.131 ± .003
Zn ^c	60	0.143	0.140 ± .002
Cu ^a	40	0.120	0.118 ± .002
Co ^b	100	0.150	0.153 ± .004

chlorocomplexes, which are neutral or negatively charged are adsorbed much less than the corresponding cations.

The K_d values in acetone- HNO_3 systems are greater than the K_d values in the corresponding DMSO- HNO_3 systems for almost all the systems. This is explained by the fact that DMSO solvates the ions more than acetone and hence the DMSO solvated ions being greater in size are adsorbed less. There is however one exception. In the solvent system containing 10% organic solvent Cu, Cd and Zn have higher values in the DMSO- HNO_3 than in the acetone- HNO_3 system. This may be due to the fact that in the high water region a specific solvent effect is obtained which may be responsible for anomalous behaviour.

Results and Discussion

The following major trends emerge after a careful analysis of the results.

In all acetone- HNO_3 systems the K_d values are higher than that in the corresponding HCl systems. This is explained by the fact that in the HNO_3 systems very few complexes are formed. However, the Cl^- is a strong complex forming agent and the

A comparison of the DMSO- HNO_3 and the DMSO-HCl systems is necessary to identify the role of HCl, in conjunction with DMSO. As the chlorocomplexes in most cases are strongly solvated by DMSO, it is expected that most ions would have higher K_d values in the DMSO- HNO_3 than in the DMSO-HCl systems. This has been found to be true in most cases except for Mg, Ca, Sr, Ba and Ni. Mg, Ca, Sr and Ba do not form complexes

TABLE 6—QUANTITATIVE SEPARATION OF BISMUTH FROM NUMEROUS METAL IONS ON COLUMNS (0.8 × 10 cm) PACKED WITH DOWEX 50WX8 RESIN

Bi ^f	Taken (m mole)		Found* (m mole)		Eluent Vol. ml	
	Other ion ^g		Bi	Other ion	Bi	Other ion
0.100	Mn 0.133		0.100 ± .002	0.133 ± .001	30	55
0.100	Cu 0.120		0.100 ± .002	0.121 ± .001	30	50
0.100	Ni 0.143		0.101 ± .001	0.143 ± .001	30	40
0.100	Co 0.150		0.100 ± .001	0.148 ± .002	30	50
0.10	Cd 0.128		0.099 ± .001	0.128 ± .002	30	55
0.050	Cd 0.640		0.051 ± .003	0.644 ± .001	30	70
0.100	Zn 0.143		0.102 ± .002	0.145 ± .001	30	40
0.050	Zn 0.615		0.050 ± .002	0.618 ± .002	30	65
0.100	Ca 0.140		0.100 ± .003	0.140 ± .004	30	40
0.100	Mg 0.143		0.101 ± .001	0.144 ± .002	30	50
0.100	Sr 0.145		0.100 ± .001	0.144 ± .002	30	45

* Mean of triplicate determinations with calculated standard deviation.

a—System S₀, b—System S₁, c—System S₂, d—0.1M HCl-60% DMSO, e—0.9M HCl-90% DMSO, f—System S₄₀, g—System S₂₀.

with NO_3^- , Cl^- or DMSO and hence their K_d values should be the same in DMSO-HCl and DMSO- HNO_3 systems. This is indeed the case for 10-50% of DMSO. At higher percentage of DMSO the K_d values in the DMSO-HCl systems are higher than in the corresponding HNO_3 systems. The same trend is exhibited by Ni in 20-90% DMSO. These discrepancies need some explanation which is presented below.

There are two different equilibria which are involved: (i) the ion solvation equilibria and (ii) the ion pair formation equilibria.

At low solvent concentration ion solvation is not high and hence upto 50% DMSO there is not much difference in the K_d values in DMSO-HCl and DMSO- HNO_3 media. However, at high DMSO concentrations K_d values in the DMSO-HCl systems are higher than the DMSO- HNO_3 systems. This is because at higher DMSO concentrations the HCl concentration is low and almost all protons are transferred to DMSO. Even then the non-protonated DMSO concentration is sufficiently high to permit the solvation of anions. As the Cl^- is more solvated than the NO_3^- , less Cl^- ions are available for ion pair formation than the NO_3^- ions and the K_d values in DMSO-HCl system is higher than in DMSO- HNO_3 system. This does not hold good in the acetone system because acetone does not encourage proton transfer and acetone is not such an efficient solvating agent. DMSO is known to have specific interaction with H^+ ions leading to the formation of the DMSOH^+ cations. This solvates the Cl^- ions strongly forming ion pairs of the type $\text{DMSOH}^+\dots\text{Cl}^-$.

The equilibrium equations may be postulated as:

Owing to equilibrium 1 most of the H^+ ions are utilized in protonating the DMSO. Hence they are not available to compete with alkaline earth metal ions for exchange sites and the K_d values of the alkaline earths increase. The Cl^- ions are not available for ion pair formation with metal ions partly because of equilibrium 2 and partly because DMSO has a higher dielectric constant than acetone. It now remains to explain the order of increase in the K_d values in the DMSO-HCl systems. Ba^{2+} shows the greatest increase followed by

Ca^{2+} , Sr^{2+} and Mg^{2+} . This is because of equilibrium 3. There is some solvation of the alkaline earth metal ions also. This solvation is greatest for Mg^{2+} owing to the smaller size of the cation followed by Ca^{2+} , Sr^{2+} and Ba^{2+} . Hence the increase in the K_d values of Mg is the least followed by Ca, Sr and Ba.

In almost all cases the K_d values in the DMSO-HCl systems are higher than in the corresponding acetone-HCl systems. This is explained as earlier by the fact that DMSO reacts with H^+ to form DMSOH^+ cations which being much larger in size than the protons do not compete effectively for exchange sites and therefore the K_d values in the DMSO-HCl systems are higher than in the acetone-HCl systems. The main exceptions are of Mg^{2+} , Cu^{2+} and Co^{2+} at concentrations higher than 50% DMSO by volume. Cu^{2+} and Co^{2+} are known to form negatively charged chlorocomplexes in DMSO-HCl systems. Of the various alkaline earths only Mg^{2+} is known to form negatively charged chlorocomplex^{1,9} and this explains the lower K_d of Mg^{2+} at higher DMSO concentrations.

The analytical importance of these studies has been demonstrated by some important separations summarized in Tables 5 and 6.

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